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Table of Content

1	Introduction	3
2	TNA pilots	4
2.1	International stakeholders (task 6.2)	4
2.2	Innovators in technology (task 6.3)	4
2.3	Public authorities (task 6.4)	5
3	Questionnaires	7
4	References	9
5	Appendix	10
	Questionnaire #1.....	10
	Questionnaire #2 and #3	17
	Questionnaire #4.....	19
	Questionnaire #5.....	32
	Questionnaire #6.....	33
	Questionnaire #7.....	34
	Questionnaire #8.....	35

1 Introduction

In the framework of workpackage 6, a range of innovative modalities were developed and explored to engage new groups of stakeholders in accessing services offered by atmospheric research infrastructures (RI). Previously, transnational access (TNA) was only offered to a single facility in a specific RI and to a smaller group of stakeholders.

Within the scope of task 6.1, a design concept for engaging with the stakeholders of interest was developed (Wenger 2022). Based on inputs from both users and access providers in surveys and during a stakeholder workshop (Wenger et al. 2021), it was concluded that co-designing access strategies together with the stakeholders will lead to the most effective outcome, as emerging user needs can be directly addressed. TNA pilots for three different groups of stakeholders were investigated: international stakeholders (task 6.2), innovators in technology (task 6.3), and public authorities (task 6.4). The individual mechanisms and developed services of the different TNA pilots were elucidated in the deliverables D6.2 to D6.4 (Rivier et al. 2023; Athanasopoulou 2023; Nicolae, Petracca Altieri, and Wenger 2023).

In this report, the process of developing the new and customised TNA modalities within the tasks 6.2 to 6.4 is summarised. The feedback of the different user groups was gathered by issuing surveys with the results evaluated and presented in the forthcoming deliverable D6.5. Table 1 summarises the different TNA pilots, stakeholders involved in the process, and the number of surveys issued. A more detailed description of the surveys can be found in Table 2 and in the 5 Appendix.

Table 1. Overview of the different TNA pilots, involved stakeholders, as well as the number of surveys issued. More details on the specific developed services and the surveys will be discussed in Sections 0 to 0.

Tasks	6.2	6.3	6.4
Target users	International stakeholders	Innovators in technology	Public authorities
Lead beneficiary	INOE	CNRS	NOA
Involved stakeholders	ESA, EUMETSAT	Private sector	ACTRIS, ICLEI-EU, RI-URBANS, ATMO ACCESS facility providers
No. surveys	3 ^a	2 ^{a,b}	5 ^a

^a Including task-specific questions as part of the survey of the stakeholder workshop;

^b No task-specific questionnaire was issued. General user feedback is evaluated instead.

2 TNA pilots

2.1 International stakeholders (task 6.2)

The goal of task 6.2 (Figure 1) was to explore new TNA modalities that are tailored to requirements and needs of international stakeholders. Three pilot projects were designed and implemented in collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). The TNA pilot projects focussed on the available services provided by atmospheric research facilities for the calibration/validation (Cal/Val) of European Earth Observation missions and instruments.

Figure 1. The timeline of all activities of Task 6.2.

2.2 Innovators in technology (task 6.3)

In task 6.3 (Figure 2), new TNA modalities were investigated focusing on innovators in technology. The ATMObox having space for up to eight mid- to low-cost sensors was developed and instrumental service offered. The device can either be used for monitoring air quality on a campaign base or for calibrating sensors against reference instruments. The service is supported by the ATC Metrology Lab: Mlab of the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) network and and by the ACTRIS Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas) at the Insitute Mines Telecom (IMT). The service was launched beginning of 2024.

Figure 2. The timeline and workflow of task 6.2.

2.3 Public authorities (task 6.4)

Task 6.4 (Figure 3) has explored new trans-national access (TNA) modalities for public authorities (Leader: NOA, participants: UCC, INOE, CNRS, FZJ). Public authorities (PA) responsible for measuring, reporting and acting on air pollution (local government, civil protection and environmental/ health agencies) need atmospheric measurements. Atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RIs) have excellent potential to support the efforts of and informed decision making by the public authorities in this area. The purpose of this task has been to identify the specific needs of public authorities, develop flexible and tailored modalities for access to multiple components from the atmospheric RIs and perform a TNA activity involving the ATMO-ACCESS European atmospheric research facilities and public authorities from Europe.

Figure 3. The timeline of all activities and main outputs of Task 6.4, towards a proposal for the public sector for TNA to ATMO-ACCESS facilities.

3 Questionnaires

Table 2. Questionnaires issued in the frame of ATMO-ACCESS WP6.

No	Title	In the frame of T6.x	Stakeholders addressed	Goal(s)	Number of participants	Issue date
1	"Questionnaire for providers and users"	T6.2, T6.3, T6.4	Users (public sector) and Providers (ATMO-ACCESS RI community)	Co-design of the pilot access of PAs to RIs	160	27/10/2021
2	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.2	ESA, EUMETSAT (stakeholders), access providers	Feedback and recommendations at mid-term of pilots' implementation	33	13/03/2024
3	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.2	ESA, EUMETSAT (stakeholders), access providers	Feedback and recommendations at end of pilots' implementation	N/A	01/03/2025
4	"Private sector user feedback"	T6.3	Private sector	Feedback on the TNA application and the services provided	16	2021-2025
5	"Questionnaire for access providers"	T6.4	Facility providers: Representatives from the RIs of ATMO-ACCESS	Initial interest of access providers, input on the nature of the pilot	30	23/07-27/8/08/2021

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6	"Questionnaire to collect user needs"	T6.4	Public authorities	Co-design of the pilot access of RIs by PAs	5	16/03/2023
7	"Questionnaire to collect provider capacities"	T6.4	Facility providers: Representatives from the RIs of ATMO-ACCESS	Preferences/availability of facility reps. For access by PAs	8	11/2023
8	"Questionnaire to collect recommendations"	T6.4	Public authorities	Evaluation and sustainability of T6.4	164*	04/10/- 30/11/2024

* The dissemination of the events was intensive, not only through the ATMO-ACCESS list (RI-Urbans contacts included), but also through the WHO Breathlife2030 newsletter.

4 References

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- Nicolae, Doina, Rosa Maria Petracca Altieri, und John Wenger. 2023. „Proposed TNA pilot for international stakeholders“. Deliverable 6.2. INOE, CNR, UCC. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/09/ATMO-ACCESS_D6.2_M30.pdf.
- Rivier, Leonard, O. Laurent, S. Sauvage, und R. Petracca. 2023. „Proposed TNA pilot for innovators in technology“. Deliverable 6.3. CNRS. https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/05/D6.3_Proposed-TNA-pilots-for-innovators-in-technology-1.pdf.
- Wenger, John. 2022. „General design concept for flexible access modalities“. Deliverable 6.1. UCC. <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2022/07/ATMO-ACCESS-Deliverable-6.1-M15-vf.pdf>.
- Wenger, John, Eleni Athanasopoulou, Doina Nicolae, und Leonard Rivier. 2021. „Stakeholder Workshop“. <https://www.atmo-access.eu/event/atmo-access-stakeholder-workshop/>.

5 Appendix

Questionnaire #1

ATMO ACCESS WP6 Slido Poll during the Stakeholder Workshop, 27 October 2021

I. Users (multiple choice)

What services are you most interested in ?

- Access to facilities, instruments, testing (66%)
- Testing and quality/standards compliance validation of instruments and processes (62%)
- Access to data, modelling (51%)
- Access to specialised training (49%)
- Access to basic training on atmospheric sciences / MOOCs (31%)
- Provision of space and logistics support for custom development and trials (14%)

Which type of access are you most interested in?

- Physical access - *Physical access is "hands-on" access when Users physically visit an infrastructure/facility* (71%)
- Remote access - *Remote access is access to resources and services offered without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility* (48%)
- Virtual access - *Virtual access is free access to Users provided through communication networks* (37%)

Which type of facilities are you interested in using?

- Observation Platforms (82%)
- Simulation Chamber Facilities (33%)
- Central Laboratories (53%)
- Mobile Platforms (62%)

Which innovative modes of access are you interested in ?

- Combinations of remote and physical access (70%)
 - Combinations of training and scientific delivery / innovation (66%)
 - Cross-disciplinary access from beyond atmospheric science (39%)
 - Simultaneous or sequential access to multiple facilities (38%)
 - Simultaneous access by users from multiple sectors (36%)
 - Piloting the use of facilities for novel purposes (31%)
 - ATMO platforms offering access for the first time (21%)
- #### II. Providers (multiple choice)

What services are you planning to provide?

- Access to facilities, instruments, testing (80%)
- Access to specialised training (53%)
- Testing and quality/standards compliance validation of instruments and processes (51%)
- Access to data, modelling (49%)
- Access to basic training on atmospheric sciences / MOOCs (27%)
- Support for the development of data products and applications (25%)
- Provision of space and logistics support for custom development and trials (22%)

Which type of access are you planning to provide?

- *Physical access - Physical access is "hands-on" access when Users physically visit an infrastructure/facility (90%)*
- *Remote access - Remote access is access to resources and services offered without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility (71%)*
- *Virtual access - Virtual access is free access to Users provided through communication networks (44%)*

Which type of facilities are you offering in ATMO-ACCESS?

- Observation Platforms (66%)
- Simulation Chamber Facilities (21%)
- Central Laboratories (21%)
- Mobile Platforms (21%)

Which innovative modes of access are you interested in?

- Combinations of remote and physical access (84%)
- Combinations of training and scientific delivery / innovation (60%)
- Cross-disciplinary access from beyond atmospheric science (40%)
- Simultaneous access by users from multiple sectors (36%)
- Piloting the use of facilities for novel purposes (36%)
- Simultaneous or sequential access to multiple facilities (32%)
- ATMO platforms offering access for the first time (14%)

III. Pilot 1

A. *Multiple choice*

Why do you think that TNAs are not generally used for Cal/Val activities?

- I don't know (43%)
- Not sufficiently known (35%)
- Too bureaucratic (26%)
- Available only through short-term projects (24%)
- Not sufficiently flexible (17%)
- Too complicated (11%)
- Lack of control from the stakeholders point of view (9%)
- Facilities open for TNA are not relevant for Cal/Val activities (4%)

What kind of TNA project would fit better to Cal/Val needs?

- Long-term TNA (e.g. correlative observations from multiple stations, FRMs) (67%)
- Short-term TNA (e.g. intensive observations campaigns, combination of platforms) (33%)
- TNA is not proper for Cal/Val activities (0%)

What would be your preferred level of complexity for this pilot?

- Targeted TNA (access to data / access to calibration labs / training / consultancy / algorithm development, etc) (11%)
- Multi-aspect TNA (combination of access to data, access to facilities, access to expertise, training, etc.) (18%)
- Depending on the situation (co-designed with the stakeholder) (69%)
- No preference (2%)

B. *Open text*

What would be your primary expectation for this TNA pilot?

- Provide access to a wider scientific community

- Determining the degree of reliability and testing/verification the capacity of the infrastructure with respect on the stakeholder demands.
- Strong collaborations
- I am curious whether and which communities outside of ACTRIS show interest in the TNA services.
- General challenge: top down vs bottom up. European scale coordination tends to amplify the value of RI products while vanishing the visibility of the average user. So far many initiative happen heavily top-down with potential NF-type contributors learning about it at very late stages. Therefore co-design also with balancing top-down vs bottom up (not for each activity but allowing for both).
- To establish flexible and clear access tools/procedures between providers and users
- A lot of applications and great projects
- Long-term, multi-site access
- Simple, flexible and clear process
- Collaboration on with EarthCARE on Cal/Val preparation for Aerosol and Cloud properties validation and best practices (including intercalibration of ground, airborne and with other non-ACTRIS networks), in a way that is useful also for Aeolus Follow On (Aerosol) and AOS (was ACCP) Cloud and Aerosol.
- Respond to a demand expressed by stakeholders
- Synergy between observational data from multiple platform
- Test data and test access in order to consolidate long term cal/val needs
- More complementary research, establishment of synergies from different areas where possible.
- Fostering the wide and advanced use of Individual but even combined RIs

IV. Pilot 2 (open text)

Why are you as an innovator in industry interested in access to research infrastructures?

- To know needs To adapt products
- Optimizing instrumentation
- Usability of measurement systems for air quality and greenhouse gases that have been tested with research standards
- Unicity of the platform to test in specific conditions and possible certification for the condition of use of the instrument for atmospheric measurements
- To get a recognized quality label
- Access to advanced reference ~~instruments~~ ~~instruments~~ together with expertise
- Access to different validation measurements for new technology
- Rigorous and certified assessment of uncertainties.
- Testing of prototypes in the central labs (comparison with reference instruments)
- Help with training, optimization, and development/improvement of our instruments along with new/exciting research

What are the major obstacles for technology innovators accessing RIs?

- Information about services available
- Training/experience of user
- Fear for IPR management in a international context
- NA

What improvements would you suggest to make RIs more accessible to innovators, particularly in the private sector?

- ATMO-ACCESS is the good step forward - have a dedicated liaison officer - Private sector working group is a good idea
- Efficient process for access: time, resources, bureaucracy
- They need a central resource to go to find where the access is
- Rolling TNA calls.
- Target communication to private sector

What types of activity and access would you propose for this TNA pilot?

- Remote-sensing retrieval evaluation with airborne or ground-based in-situ measurements
- Identification of new parameters / species that the community needs most / wish lists
- A combination of TNA to CFs and TNA to multi-parameter NFs to benefit from top-level single parameter testing and response to complex mixture testing.
- Instrument intercomparisons for specific applications
- Support of national access, not only international access
- Recurrent access to central labs
- Specific call reserved for private sector to increase visibility ?

III. Pilot 3

A. *Multiple choice*

What type of events/information/services would you consider to be high priority in relation to your work?

- Natural episodes (e.g. pollen, dust) (67%)
- Assessment of air pollution events (56%)
- Smoke plumes from (peri-)urban fires (54%)
- Source apportionment (near real time, annual/seasonal) (46%)
- Real-time information, alarm systems (46%)
- Transboundary air pollution (46%)
- Toxic plumes from industrial accidents (44%)
- Mapping, hot spots identification (28%)
- Extreme weather events (23%)
- Support for guidelines/standardization (21%)
- Policy/mitigation/climate scenario analysis (18%)
- Past assessment/reporting on pollution levels and exceedances (8%)

Is your National Infrastructure/Regulatory network sufficient to cover your needs in atmospheric monitoring, decision making, public information etc?

- No (18%)
- Yes (82%)

B. *Open text*

What type of events/information/services would you consider to be high priority in relation to your work?

- Please, list and/or comment on emerging needs for atmospheric monitoring due to new, upcoming regulations, targets etc.
- An online monitor (s) for viruses !!!
- Health guidelines for some "new" pollutants are unknown (BC, PNC) reasonable cost measurement for some compounds mentioned in the new directive (NH₃, PNC, pollen, pesticide)
- Uptake of new observation methodologies by the operational agencies
- Urban Quality Air (with related measurement uncertainties)
- Regulating footprints from air traffic.

- A requirement for measurement and unambiguous characterisation of semivolatile organic compounds or "condensables" will be required for CLRTAP / Gothenburg protocol compliance. This requires technology / instrument / technique development as well as deployment
- Better evaluation of PM toxicity
- New technology capability and new data analysis tools
- Young people working on that!!!
- Verification of GHG emissions for carbon-neutral and net-zero pathways
- Human resources ?
- Monitoring greenhouse gases in urban areas?
- We are not really monitoring, so how we should know this? for sure more contact with monitoring agencies in needed
- LIDAR modules?
- Need for individual exposure determination
- Indoors air quality
- Demand is high, but costly
- Dealing with extreme pollution events may need to be able to mobilize mobile instruments from different places in Europe to help
- Rigorous assessment of data uncertainty, homogeneity of datasets, certified calibration.

Mention any good practices from the past or your personal view for access modalities to research infrastructures RIs

- Research groups already used TNA networks to get in contact with stations to do measurements for specific questions (pollution, pollen, etc.) , ATMO-ACCESS can support here and can work as an communicator
- Users should (digitally) sign a protocol in order to protect IPR and data ownership
- Access to tailored (simplified) data products from observational platforms

Which challenges have you already experienced or expect to face for utilizing trans-national access (TNA) to research infrastructures (RIs)?

- Weather timing of the access application in combination with the calls billing modalities
- Limited budget of TNA (higher actual costs than covered by TNA)
- Bureaucracy and costs of equipment shipping abroad.
- Time constants to line up on short notice.
- Need to access national platforms within "TNA" scheme
- Complex paper-work

Questionnaire #2 and #3

Questionnaire to collect recommendations

Pilot for international stakeholders

1 Introduction

The European Commission intends to revise the TNA programs. Our particular interest would be to understand how the stakeholders can use such a program in order to take advantage of the coordinated European research infrastructures like ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS.

2 Main question to be answered

Considering your experience up to now with the ATMO pilot for international stakeholder, what would you recommend to EC for the future TNA programs?

3 Questions

1. What is your role in the ATMO-ACCESS pilot projects for international stakeholders? **Single choice**
 - I represent a stakeholder
 - I represent an ATMO-ACCESS provider
 - I represent an access provider but not an ATMO-ACCESS beneficiary
2. Why do you think that international stakeholders (e.g. international organisations) have not accessed the TNA programs in their classical form? **Multiple choices**
 - Because they did not know about this opportunity
 - Because they did not understand the concept and the vocabulary
 - Because of the trans-national constraints
 - Because of the bureaucracy
 - Because of the "single-facility" approach
 - Because of the "competitive" approach
 - Other, please comment
3. What are the main benefits of the ATMO-ACCESS pilot projects for international stakeholders, from your perspective? **Multiple choices**
 - Transparency of the whole process (through community meetings and collaborative environment)
 - Coordination (through the RI)
 - Direct involvement of the stakeholder in the planning and reporting
 - Involvement of many and diverse facilities and expertise
 - Combination of various access modalities (physical + remote + virtual)
 - Reduced bureaucracy considering the complexity of the pilot projects
 - Guidance in the estimation of effort (through the RI experts)
 - Guidance in the implementation of the activities (through the RI and the stakeholder experts)
 - Opportunity to be partially funded (e.g. through ATMO-ACCESS or national projects)
 - Flexibility in adjusting the access during the implementation, to serve the "last-minute" needs of the stakeholder
 - Value for money (results versus effort)
 - Other, please comment

4. What is not properly addressed / organised currently in the ATMO-ACCESS pilot projects for international stakeholders? **Multiple choices**
 - The selection process was too long and complicated
 - The effort is higher than available resources
 - There are too many meetings and reports to fill
 - The duration of the projects is too short compared to the Cal/Val needs
 - Other, please comment
5. Knowing now the difficulties, would you participate in a future similar project? **Single choice**
 - No, the result does not justify the effort (please comment)
 - No, the funding does not cover the effort (please comment)
 - Maybe, with some optimisations (please comment)
 - Yes, the pilots have demonstrated their utility (please comment)
6. Should the EC consider dedicated TNA programs for international stakeholders and RIs?
Single choice
 - No, the RIs can arrange their own access provision programs, and use their funds
 - No, the stakeholder can arrange their own programs to fund projects involving RIs or selected facilities
 - Yes, EC support is needed because funds are limited at the side of the RIs and of the stakeholder
 - Yes, EC should develop such a program in order to maximise the impact of the RIs beyond the scientific world (cascade effect through the stakeholder)
 - Other, please comment
7. What would be the main features of such a dedicated TNA program for international stakeholders and RIs? **Multiple choices**
 - Simplified process for accessing the RI's facilities (expression of interest >>> preliminary acceptance >>> detailed planning >>> implementation and reporting)
 - Co-design of the projects (stakeholder + providers)
 - Co-coordination (stakeholder + RI)
 - Co-funding (EC + stakeholder + RI + providers, various ratios)
 - Combined access modalities
 - Combined facilities
 - Open access to results
 - Other, please comment
8. Imagine you are the decision-maker at EC side. What would you change in the current TNA programs, to make it useful for the international stakeholders? **Free text**

ATMO-ACCESS User Feedback & TNA Carbon Footprint Assessment Questionnaire

ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from user groups granted with TNA in the frame of the project.

Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS community (TNA management Team, Strategic TNA Board, Project coordination, Facilities and Providers) understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better.

The questionnaire consists of a series of questions about different aspects of your access experience (communication, access procedures, scientific/technical services, support services).

The questionnaire must be submitted once by each user group as soon as the TNA ends. All replies will be treated in the strictest confidence. The information given will only be used for monitoring and assessment purposes.

By submitting this form, you are also giving us permission to contact you.

*** Required**

1. Privacy notice *

The ATMO-ACCESS privacy notice can be accessed at this link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/atmo-access-privacy-policy/>

Check all that apply.

I agree with the ATMO-ACCESS privacy policy and terms of use

2. First Name

3. Last Name

4. Home institution

5. Title & Acronym of the TNA project *

6. Facility accessed *

Check all that apply.

- AGORA, ES (OBS)
- ATMOS, GR (OBS)
- BCN, ES (OBS)
- CAO, CY (OBS)
- CESAR, NL (OBS)
- CIAO, IT (OBS)
- CMN-PV, IT (OBS)
- CO-PDD, FR (OBS)
- EVASO, PT (OBS)
- FKL, GR (OBS)
- FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)
- HTM, SE (OBS)
- ISAF - (IZO), ES (OBS)
- JFJ, CH (OBS)
- Melpitz, DE (OBS)
- NAOK, CZ (OBS)
- OPAR, FR (OBS)
- RADO, RO (OBS)
- SBO, AT (OBS)
- SIRT, FR (OBS)
- SMEAR II, FI (OBS)
- WOS, PL (OBS)
- ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE (ASC)
- AIDA, DE (ASC)
- AURA, DK (ASC)
- CESAM, FR (ASC)
- ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)
- ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)
- EUPHORE, ES (ASC)
- HELIOS, FR (ASC)
- IASC, IE (ASC)
- KASCs, FI (ASC)
- MAC, UK (ASC)
- PACS-C2, CH (ASC)
- QUAREC, DE (ASC)
- SAPHIR, DE (ASC)

- FCoMLab, FI (MOB)
- FORTH-MSU, GR (MOB)
- LACROS, DE (MOB)
- USRL, CY (MOB)
- CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)
- ICOS-ATC, FR (CL)
- WCCAP, DE (CL)
- ACMCC @SIRTA, FR (CL)
- CCRES-FR @SIRTA, FR (CL)
- CCRES-NL @CESAR, NL (CL)
- ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)
- CARS-RO @RADO, RO (CL)
- CARS-CNR @CIAO, IT (CL)
- CARS-ES @ISAF, ES (CL)
- CCice @AIDA, DE (CL)

7. How did you first find out about the possibilities of access supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project?

Check all that apply.

- ATMO-ACCESS website
- Research infrastructure websites (please specify in other)
- Direct mailing from Research infrastructure (please specify in other)
- Social media (please specify in other)
- Information received by colleagues/personal contacts
- Information received at event (please specify in other)

Other: _____

8. Without the support of the ATMO-ACCESS funding, would you have been able to access the facility?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 10*
- No

9. If no, please indicate the reason

Check all that apply.

- Not otherwise eligible to apply for access to the infrastructure/s
- Unable to pay a (possible) user fee
- Unable to pay travel & subsistence for one or more of the group members

Other: _____

Skip to question 11

Untitled section

10. If yes, please give details or indicate possible co-funding options

Evaluate the services provided
by ATMO-ACCESS

Please assess the following points rating them on a scale from 'very poor' to 'very good'.
(0 = very poor, 1 = poor, 2 = fair, 3 = good, 4 = very good, 5 = excellent).

11. Please evaluate the ACCESS SERVICES

Please rate all the elements

Mark only one oval per row.

	0	1	2	3	4	5
Publicity and information about the access	<input type="radio"/>					
Practical information on how to apply (documentation, FAQs, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
Application form (length, information required, easyness)	<input type="radio"/>					
Interaction with and support by the TNA Team	<input type="radio"/>					
Duration of the selection process	<input type="radio"/>					
Quantity of post-access documentation required	<input type="radio"/>					

12. Please indicate any comments or suggestions you would like to make on the ACCESS SERVICES

13. Please evaluate the FACILITY/IES' SERVICES

Please provide at least 5 ratings. Leave blank when the point is not applicable

Mark only one oval per row.

	0	1	2	3	4	5
Information and support for organizing the access	<input type="radio"/>					
Scientific and technical support to conduct your research and interpret the results	<input type="radio"/>					
Technical support for your instruments (calibrations)	<input type="radio"/>					
Logistic support at the facility (space, computing, libraries, accommodation)	<input type="radio"/>					
Administrative support (including the reimbursement of travel & subsistence expenses)	<input type="radio"/>					
Overall appreciation of the services accessed	<input type="radio"/>					

14. Please indicate any comments or suggestions you would like to make on the FACILITY/IES' SERVICES

15. Please evaluate the overall service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS TNA
Please rate together both the ACCESS SERVICES and the FACILITY/IES' SERVICES

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Excellent					

16. If your evaluation is ≤ 2 , please briefly explain why:

17. Shortly comment the benefits of the TNA and/or lessons learnt

18. Has the TNA led to new discovery, breakthroughs, novelties...?

19. Has the access via TNA contributed to filling a patent or to the design of a prototype?

20. Do you have any further comments/ suggestions for improvement?

TNA CARBON FOOTPRINT ASSESSMENT

21. Type of access realized

Mark only one oval.

- Physical (hands-on access of user at the facility)
- Remote access (the user does not visit the facility in person)
Skip to question 27
- Combination of Physical and Remote access *Skip to question 31*

Physical Access

22. Travel mode

If you took 2 DIFFERENT MEANS OF TRANSPORT, please treat these as separate trips

Check all that apply.

- Air (<1000km)
- Air (1000-3500km)
- Air (>3500km)
- Train (national<200km)
- Train (national>200km)
- Train (neighbour countries)
- Train (international)
- Car (fuel)
- Car (hybrid)
- Car (electric)
- Bus

23. Amount of identical trips

E.g. If 3 DIFFERENT flights have been taken from the same departure and arrival locations, insert 3. Otherwise, insert 1. It is NOT the number of passengers on the SAME mean of transport. If 30 people get the same bus, insert 1. If one person gets one bus, and one person gets ANOTHER bus, that both do the same trip, insert 2.

24. Departure city - Arrival city

25. Was your trip one way or return?

If you took 2 DIFFERENT MEANS OF TRANSPORT, please treat these as separate trips

Mark only one oval.

- One way
- Return

26. Distance travelled (in km)

Remote Access

27. Participants (number)

Insert number of participants in the remote event

28. Insert remote event duration time in MINUTES (min)

For online meetings taking place over a number of days, estimate total duration of meeting (mins)

29. Webcams

Select if webcams were kept on or off by participants. If intermittent (eg. only turning camera on when asking a question), select off.

Check all that apply.

On

Off

30. Screensharing

Select if screensharing was activated. e.g. if meeting participants gave presentations requiring screensharing. If intermittent (eg. only sporadic screensharing), select off.

Mark only one oval.

On

Off

Combination of Physical and Remote Access

PHYSICAL PART OF THE ACCESS

31. Travel mode

If you took 2 DIFFERENT MEANS OF TRANSPORT, please treat these as separate trips

Check all that apply.

- Air (<1000km)
- Air (1000-3500km)
- Air (>3500km)
- Train (national<200km)
- Train (national>200km)
- Train (neighbour countries)
- Train (international)
- Car (fuel)
- Car (hybrid)
- Car (electric)
- Bus

32. Amount of identical trips

E.g. If 3 DIFFERENT flights have been taken from the same departure and arrival locations, insert 3. Otherwise, insert 1. It is NOT the number of passengers on the SAME mean of transport. If 30 people get the same bus, insert 1. If one person gets one bus, and one person gets ANOTHER bus, that both do the same trip, insert 2.

33. Departure city - Arrival city

34. Was your trip one way or return?

If you took 2 DIFFERENT MEANS OF TRANSPORT, please treat these as separate trips

Mark only one oval.

One way

Return

35. Distance travelled (in km)

REMOTE PART OF THE ACCESS

36. Participants (number)

Insert number of participants in the remote event

37. Insert remote event duration time in MINUTES (min)

For online meetings taking place over a number of days, estimate total duration of meeting (mins)

38. Webcams

Select if webcams were kept on or off by participants. If intermittent (eg. only turning camera on when asking a question), select off.

Check all that apply.

On

Off

39. **Screensharing**

Select if screensharing was activated. e.g. if meeting participants gave presentations requiring screensharing. If intermittent (eg. only sporadic screensharing), select off.

Mark only one oval.

On

Off

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Questionnaire #5

Pilot TNA(s) for public authorities

Objective: to design pilot TNA(s) for public authorities that need access to atmospheric measurements for routine monitoring or the characterization/assessment of atmospheric episodes e.g. industrial accidents, air pollution events, extreme weather and related natural hazards.

Example of a potential pilot: Provision of air quality information by involving ATMO-ACCESS TNA providers operating (in situ) Atmospheric Observation Facilities and/or Mobile Platforms. Simulation Chamber Facilities and Central Laboratories could also be involved by providing information on cal/val of sensors and networks, threshold assessment support, exposure studies and source identification.

Contact person: Eleni Athanasopoulou, eathana@noa.gr

- Are you interested in contributing to development of a pilot in this area? Y/N boxes
- Are you interested in contributing to development of the proposed potential pilot? Y/N boxes.
- Do you have any ideas for other pilots in this area? Y/N – If yes please provide details.
- Please provide contact details for other organisations, institutes, companies, public authorities or individuals that you think may be interested in contributing to the development of a pilot in this area or in exploiting the atmospheric data/outputs that may be generated.

Questionnaire addressed to ICLEI-EU members (representatives from city authorities)

Slido Questions for Potential Users

- 1) Which type of access are you most interested in? **(multiple choices)**
 - Physical access (Physical access is “hands-on” access when Users physically visit an infrastructure/facility)
 - Remote access (Remote access is access to resources and services offered without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility)
 - Virtual access (Virtual access is free access to Users provided through communication networks)

- 2) Which innovative modes of access are you interested in ? **(multiple choices)**
 - a) combinations of remote and physical access
 - b) combinations of training and scientific delivery / innovation
 - c) cross-disciplinary access from beyond atmospheric science
 - d) simultaneous or sequential access to multiple facilities
 - e) simultaneous access by users from multiple sectors
 - f) piloting the use of facilities for novel purposes
 - g) ATMO platforms offering access for the first time
 - h) none of the above

- 3) Your emerging needs potentially addressed at/covered by RIs abroad **(multiple choices)** :
 - a. Health guidelines relevant to 'new' pollutants (eg BC, PNC), which our National facilities are not able/competent to perform or necessitate collaboration with expertise/facilities from abroad
 - b. Compliance to upcoming/new protocols/Directives/rules on air pollution through a transnational collaboration
 - c. Certified calibration of atmospheric monitoring instrument(s)
 - d. Access to AQ monitoring data produces/owned by a transnational research infrastructure
 - e. Source apportionment of air pollution (e.g. through a local campaign with portable instrumentation)
 - f. Specialized training on e.g. new/ novel atmospheric monitoring instrumentation,

- 4) Please, provide our contact details for your participation in the Working Group of the TNA call for Public Authorities: Full Name, Organization, e-mail (e.g. Eleni Athanasopoulou, NOA, eathana@noa.gr)

Questionnaire #7

Questionnaire targeting the facility representatives who expressed interest and capability to support the TNA activity titled “Challenges for the public sector to meet the upcoming revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive” (November 2023)

Section 1: Please, select your contribution to the preparatory webinar/ virtual training of public authorities (prior to their visit to your facility)

- Overview of upcoming changes in the EC Directive
- Purpose of additional pollutants with respect to health, ecosystems, climate etc.
- Purpose of complementary AQ measurements by low-cost sensors
- Issues of QA/QC of sensor measurements

Section 2: Please, select the topic(s) you wish your facility provides support to the visiting PAs

- Guidance on sampling point representativeness
- Design of monitoring network Guidance on monitoring and reference methods for BC, NH₃, UFP (PN)
- Guidance on the application of low-cost sensors
- Support the deployment of sensor networks
- Training on QA/QC protocols

Section 3: Please, select the modality of access offered by your facility. Then, indicate the timeframe your facility is available for this pilot.

- physical access
- remote access (e.g. through a portable web-camera)
- start date of pilot
- end date of pilot

Questionnaire to collect recommendations

Pilot for public authorities

Introduction

The European Commission intends to revise the TNA programs. Our particular interest would be to understand how the stakeholders can use such a program in order to take advantage of the coordinated European research infrastructures like ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS.

Part A:

1. From which country do you come from? **Free text**
2. Do you represent a public authority? If yes, which one? **Free text**
3. Have you participated in any ATMO-ACCESS activity before? **Yes/no**
4. Have you participated in the 1st webinar of this activity? **Yes/no**
5. Have you participated in the 2nd webinar of this activity? **Yes/no**

Part B:

6. Have you participated in the ATMO-ACCESS co-design working group meetings towards the trans-national access (TNA) opportunity for public authorities? **Yes/no**
- 6a. If the answer to the previous question was no, why? **Multiple choices**
 - Because I did not know about this opportunity
 - Because I did not understand the concept and the vocabulary
 - Because of the trans-national constraints
 - Because of language issue
 - Because of time constraints (unavailability during the proposed timeframes)
- 6b. If the answer to the previous question was YES, which of the below were appreciated by you? **Multiple choices**
 - Collaborative environment
 - Direct involvement of the stakeholder in the planning of the activity
 - Other, please comment **Free text**
7. These webinars are the final outcome of the ATMO-ACCESS pilot project 'Trans-national access for public authorities', in collaboration with RI-URBANS. What are the main benefits of such opportunities from your perspective? **Multiple choices**
 - The online (rather than physical) format of the event
 - The involvement of experts from multiple facilities and countries
 - The opportunity to interact with these experts (rather than watching a video)
 - The targeted talks to critical issues
 - The open and free of charge format
 - Other, please comment **Free text**
8. Apart from and beyond your need to get insights for the upcoming revisions of the EC AQ guidelines, what type of events/information/services would you consider to be high priority in relation to your work? **Multiple choices**
 - Natural episodes (e.g. pollen, dust)
 - Assessment of air pollution events
 - Smoke plumes from (peri-)urban fires
 - Source apportionment (near real time, annual/seasonal)
 - Real-time information, alarm systems

- Transboundary air pollution
 - Toxic plumes from industrial accidents
 - Mapping, hot spots identification
 - Extreme weather events
 - Support for guidelines/standardization
 - Policy/mitigation/climate scenario analysis
 - Past assessment/reporting on pollution levels and exceedances
 - Other, please comment **Free text**
9. Should the European Commission consider dedicated trans-national access (TNA) programs for public authorities and Research Infrastructures (RIs)? **Multiple choices**
- No, the RIs can arrange their own access provision programs, and use their funds
 - No, the stakeholder can arrange their own programs to fund projects involving RIs or selected facilities
 - Yes, EC support is needed because funds are limited at the side of the RIs and of the stakeholder
 - Yes, EC should develop such a program in order to maximise the impact of the RIs beyond the scientific world (cascade effect through the stakeholder)
 - Other, please comment **Free text**
10. What would be the main features of such a dedicated TNA program for public authorities and RIs? **Multiple choices**
- Simplified process for accessing the RI facilities (expression of interest >>> preliminary acceptance >>> detailed planning >>> implementation and reporting)
 - Co-design of the projects (stakeholder + providers)
 - Co-funding (EC + stakeholder + RI + providers, various ratios)
 - Combined access modalities (physical, virtual, remote)
 - Combined access to facilities (visit more than one)
 - Open access to results

Part C:

11. Imagine you are the decision-maker at EC side. What would you change in the current TNA programs, to make it useful for the public authorities? **Free text**
12. Suggestions for Future Webinars **Free text**
13. Have these webinars met your expectations? **1, 2, 3, 4, 5**
14. Questions /Comments /Requests **Free text**
15. Other **Free text**

